

Vision-Based Segmentation and Morphometric Measurement of Flatfish Using an Enhanced GrabCut Approach

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Abstract

This work presents a fully automated, non-contact vision system for morphometric measurement of flatfish juveniles under real hatchery conditions. The proposed method relies exclusively on deterministic computer-vision techniques and is designed to operate robustly in environments characterised by humidity, variable illumination and heterogeneous conveyor backgrounds. Fish silhouettes are extracted using an enhanced GrabCut segmentation pipeline that integrates colour-based priors and spatial constraints to stabilise foreground estimation without the need for annotated datasets or machine-learning models. A chromatic detector is used to identify the conveyor belt and define a dynamic region of interest, while morphometric features—including total length, width and projected area—are computed via PCA-based geometric analysis. To convert pixel measurements into millimetres, metric scaling is obtained through a PINHOLE-based formulation, $s = \frac{H \cdot p}{f}$, which leverages intrinsic camera parameters and fixed imaging geometry, avoiding the operational limitations of physical calibration targets in wet environments. The system operates in real time and integrates natively into an IoT/Node-RED architecture for data persistence and process monitoring. Results demonstrate high accuracy, operational robustness and suitability for industrial deployment, providing a scalable solution for automated grading, growth monitoring and biomass estimation in precision aquaculture. This article forms part of the FLATCLASS RD project (IG408M.2025.000.000072), funded by IGAPE under the IA360 programme, aimed at fostering artificial intelligence technologies to accelerate the digital transformation of the Galician productive sector.

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1. Introduction

The digital transformation of aquaculture is increasingly supported by advances in computer vision and automated sensing technologies. Non-contact morphometric measurement has become a key component of precision aquaculture, enabling accurate estimation of biomass, growth rate and size distribution without the handling stress associated with manual measurements. Vision-based systems, in particular, provide a fast, scalable and non-invasive alternative and have been widely explored for species identification, sorting, grading and biometric assessment. Early contributions demonstrated the feasibility of extracting total length, body width and other morphometric traits using classical image-processing techniques based on thresholding, contour detection and morphological filtering [2], [6]. These methods established the foundation for modern non-contact measurement pipelines by showing that reliable morphometric information could be obtained from silhouette-based computer-vision approaches.

In parallel, recent years have seen the emergence of deep-learning methods as powerful tools for fish monitoring, segmentation and phenotyping. Convolutional neural networks and advanced segmentation architectures have been successfully applied to extract body measurements, landmarks and biomass-related traits in controlled environments [9], [11], [12], [14], [15]. While these techniques can achieve high accuracy, they typically require large annotated datasets, GPU-accelerated computation and controlled lighting conditions to avoid performance degradation due to domain shifts. Such requirements limit their suitability for

industrial hatchery environments, where illumination, humidity, reflections and background variability cannot be tightly controlled.

For flatfish species such as *Solea spp.* and *Scophthalmus maximus*, classical computer-vision methods remain highly competitive due to the favourable geometry of the animals and the operational constraints of production facilities. A landmark example is the Vision-based Automatic Measurement System (VAMS) developed by Jeong et al. [8], which used a CCD camera, a translucent conveyor and a morphological processing pipeline to achieve sub-millimetre accuracy in total-length and body-width measurement. Their approach relied on morphological opening and closing to selectively filter fins, together with edge-based pattern matching to detect key anatomical landmarks. This work demonstrated that deterministic image-processing pipelines can achieve high precision when the imaging conditions are well controlled.

However, industrial hatcheries often operate with overhead cameras and opaque conveyors, where backlighting is impractical and environmental effects such as humidity, water droplets, variable shadows and local reflections introduce significant noise. Under these conditions, segmentation must be robust to fluctuations in colour and contrast, and reliable contour extraction must be achievable without specialised illumination. Classical segmentation based on graph cuts, such as the GrabCut algorithm [5], remains an effective option under these constraints, as it leverages Gaussian Mixture Models and Markov Random Fields to produce stable foreground extraction. Recent adaptations have further demonstrated the viability of GrabCut-based pipelines

in variable underwater or aquaculture-related conditions when combined with adaptive colour modelling or region-of-interest detection [13].

Another important challenge in image-based morphometry is the conversion of pixel-based measurements into physical units. Physical calibration targets such as checkerboards are widely used in laboratory settings, but they are unsuitable for humid industrial environments where condensation, splashes and irregular illumination degrade pattern visibility. For this reason, many vision-based measurement systems adopt geometric calibration strategies based on the pinhole camera model, which provides a stable mapping between pixel measurements and millimetres using only intrinsic parameters and a fixed camera-object distance [3].

Building on these principles, this article presents a fully automated computer-vision system for non-contact morphometric measurement of flatfish juveniles under real hatchery conditions. The proposed pipeline relies exclusively on classical image-processing methods—without any machine-learning or deep-learning components—and integrates: (i) adaptive chromatic detection of the conveyor belt to isolate a stable region of interest; (ii) a reinforced GrabCut segmentation strategy guided by colour and spatial priors; (iii) PCA-based geometric analysis for extracting length, width and projected area; and (iv) a pinhole-based metric conversion model that eliminates the need for physical calibration patterns.

This vision-only approach preserves the deterministic, explainable behaviour of classical image processing while offering the robustness required for industrial deployment. By avoiding dependence on AI models, the system removes the need for annotated datasets, retraining or GPU hardware, making it suitable for embedded and edge-computing environments. Finally, it extends the classical principles established in [8] to overhead imaging, non-uniform lighting and opaque conveyors, and complements recent developments in image-based morphometry and biomass estimation [10], [16].

2. State of the art

2.1. Classical Vision-Based Approaches for Non-Contact Morphometric Measurement

Non-contact morphometric measurement has long been recognised as a key enabler of automation in fish grading and biometric assessment. Early vision-based systems demonstrated that robust length and width measurements could be obtained directly from binary silhouettes generated through thresholding and contour extraction [2], [6]. In their simplest form, segmentation is achieved via a global or adaptive threshold applied to the image $I(x, y)$:

$$B(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } I(x, y) \geq \tau, \\ 0, & \text{if } I(x, y) < \tau, \end{cases}$$

where τ may be fixed or data-driven. Morphological post-processing is then used to remove noise and restore structural continuity. The fundamental operators of erosion and dilation are defined as

$$R \ominus S = \{x \mid S_x \subseteq R\}, \quad R \oplus S = \{x \mid (S_x \cap R) \neq \emptyset\},$$

where R is the binary image and S a structuring element. From these, opening and closing follow as

$$R \circ S = (R \ominus S) \oplus S, \quad R \bullet S = (R \oplus S) \ominus S.$$

Once a clean silhouette is obtained, classical approaches extract geometric descriptors such as Feret diameters, contour curvature and principal axes. A commonly used measure is the Feret

diameter in direction θ , given by

$$F(\theta) = \max_{(x_i, x_j) \in C} \langle x_i - x_j, u(\theta) \rangle, \quad u(\theta) = (\cos \theta, \sin \theta),$$

where C denotes the contour set. The maximum projected diameter, frequently used as a proxy for body length, is computed as

$$F_{\max} = \max_{\theta \in [0, \pi]} F(\theta).$$

These deterministic pipelines became foundational in early automated grading systems due to their interpretability, low computational cost and robustness in controlled illumination conditions. Their limitations, however, become evident under variable lighting, reflections or non-uniform backgrounds, motivating the development of more specialised approaches.

2.2. Flatfish-Specific Vision Systems for Morphometric Measurement

Flatfish species such as *Solea spp.* and *Scophthalmus maximus* exhibit a dorsoventrally flattened morphology that is particularly favourable for silhouette-based morphometric extraction. Their consistent posture on conveyor systems facilitates the detection of outlines and anatomical landmarks from a single overhead image.

A canonical example is the Vision-based Automatic Measurement System (VAMS) developed by Jeong *et al.* [8]. VAMS uses a CCD camera, a translucent conveyor and controlled backlighting to generate high-contrast silhouettes. Anatomical relevance is enhanced by morphological filtering: opening suppresses narrow pectoral fins, whereas closing reinforces continuity in the caudal region.

Landmarks such as the jaw tip, caudal peduncle (CP) and tail tip are then identified to compute total length (TL). When only two landmarks are available, TL is calculated as

$$TL = \|\mathbf{p}_{\text{jaw}} - \mathbf{p}_{\text{tail}}\|,$$

where \mathbf{p}_{jaw} and \mathbf{p}_{tail} represent their respective coordinates. If an intermediate landmark at the caudal peduncle is included, the length becomes

$$TL = \|\mathbf{p}_{\text{jaw}} - \mathbf{p}_{\text{CP}}\| + \|\mathbf{p}_{\text{CP}} - \mathbf{p}_{\text{tail}}\|.$$

VAMS demonstrated that deterministic image-processing methods can achieve sub-millimetre precision under favourable imaging conditions. However, its reliance on transmitted illumination and translucent conveyors limits its applicability in many industrial hatcheries, where opaque belts, overhead cameras and humid conditions introduce strong variability. These constraints have motivated alternative segmentation and measurement pipelines that eschew backlighting while retaining deterministic behaviour.

2.3. Deep Learning-Based Morphometric Systems and Their Industrial Limitations

Deep learning has reshaped the landscape of fish monitoring, segmentation and phenotyping. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs), fully convolutional architectures and advanced segmentation models such as DeepLab have been applied to extract morphometric descriptors, anatomical landmarks and biomass-related features across a range of species [9], [12]. In these models, segmentation is formalised as the optimisation of a pixelwise classification function:

$$\hat{y}(x, y) = \arg \max_{c \in C} P(c \mid I(x, y); \theta),$$

where θ are network parameters learned from annotated datasets.

Deep-learning systems have also been used for underwater mass estimation [15], segmental biomass inference in partially occluded scenes [11], and object detection in dynamic aquaculture environments [14]. Stereo-vision pipelines augmented with neural post-processing have demonstrated accurate biomass estimation for free-swimming fish [16].

Despite their capabilities, deep-learning-based measurement systems face several constraints that reduce their suitability for real industrial hatcheries:

- **Data dependency:** high-quality annotated datasets are required for training and periodic retraining.
- **Domain shift:** humidity, water droplets, reflections and variable shadows alter pixel distributions and degrade model performance.
- **Computational requirements:** many hatchery facilities operate on embedded hardware without GPU acceleration.
- **Maintenance overhead:** the need for continual retraining conflicts with deterministic, low-maintenance industrial operation.

These limitations highlight the enduring relevance of deterministic vision pipelines—particularly those capable of robust segmentation without training data—in production environments where stability, interpretability and low computational cost are critical.

2.4. Segmentation Techniques for Robust Silhouette Extraction

Accurate silhouette extraction is essential for pixel-based morphometry. While thresholding and morphology are effective under controlled conditions, their sensitivity to illumination variations, shadows and reflections makes them unreliable in industrial facilities.

Graph-cut-based methods—and particularly GrabCut—offer a more robust formulation by modelling segmentation as an energy minimisation over a Markov Random Field [5]. The segmentation mask L is obtained by minimising:

$$E(L, \theta) = \sum_i D_i(L_i | \theta) + \lambda \sum_{(i,j)} V_{ij}(L_i, L_j), \quad (1)$$

where D_i is the GMM-based regional term and V_{ij} the smoothness term. Recent adaptations have confirmed the suitability of GrabCut for aquatic environments when combined with chromatic priors or ROI constraints [13].

Graph-cut methods thus provide a principled mechanism for stable segmentation under variable lighting, making them attractive for overhead imaging of flatfish on opaque conveyors.

2.5. Calibration Strategies for Metric Measurement

Conversion of pixel-based measurements into real-world units requires calibration. Checkerboard-based approaches are widely used in laboratories but are impractical in humid environments where condensation and fouling degrade pattern visibility.

For hatchery applications, calibration based on the PINHOLE camera model provides a robust alternative. The pixel-to-metric scale factor s is given by:

$$s = \frac{H \cdot p}{f}, \quad (2)$$

where H is the camera–object distance, p the pixel pitch and f the focal length. This formulation avoids the need for recurring calibration captures and remains stable when the imaging geometry is fixed, as shown in standard camera-calibration literature [3].

2.6. Identified Gaps and Relevance of the Present Work

The literature shows three dominant trends: (i) early deterministic silhouette-based methods [2], [6]; (ii) flatfish-specific systems relying on controlled backlighting [8]; and (iii) deep-learning approaches offering high accuracy but requiring extensive data and hardware resources [9], [11], [12], [14], [15], [16].

However, no published system addresses the full set of constraints encountered in juvenile-flatfish hatcheries:

- overhead RGB imaging on opaque blue conveyors,
- humidity, reflections and variable illumination,
- absence of backlighting or controlled optical paths,
- need for deterministic, training-free, low-latency processing,
- integration with industrial IoT architectures.

The FLATCLASS system developed in this work explicitly fills this gap by combining adaptive chromatic ROI detection, a fully automatic GrabCut-based segmentation pipeline, PCA-derived morphometric descriptors and PINHOLE-based metric conversion. This forms a robust, industrially deployable solution for automated morphometry of juvenile flatfish.

3. Material and method

The FLATCLASS vision module was implemented as a fully deterministic image-processing pipeline designed for robust, non-contact morphometric measurement of juvenile flatfish under industrial hatchery conditions. The system is composed of five stages: (i) image acquisition, (ii) preprocessing and chromatic stabilisation, (iii) segmentation and selection through an enhanced GrabCut procedure, (iv) PCA-based morphometric extraction with optional metric calibration through a PINHOLE model, and (v) Persistence data and real-time results. A flowchart of this pipeline is shown in Fig. 1. All algorithms were implemented in Python 3.11 using OpenCV 4.9, and orchestrated through Node-RED for real-time integration with the aquaculture infrastructure.

3.1. Image Acquisition

Images were acquired using a Datalogic P22C 600–000 ML industrial camera equipped with an 8 mm focal-length lens. A laser barrier provided the hardware trigger, ensuring that each fish crossing the optical gate generated one image capture. The distance between the optical centre of the camera and the plane of the fish was fixed to $H = 315\text{mm}$, and frames were transmitted via TCP to the vision service in Node-Red. Illumination was provided by a diffuse overhead LED system, with humidity and reflections typical of aquaculture environments.

Figure 2. Image acquired by the capture module.

3.2. Preprocessing and Chromatic Stabilisation

Each image I undergoes a three-step preprocessing pipeline:

Pipeline for automatic morphometric measurement of flatfish

1. Non-local means denoising (NLMeans).
2. Bilateral filtering to preserve edges.
3. Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) applied to the value channel V of the HSV model.

These operations stabilise illumination and preserve the chromatic signature of the blue conveyor belt, enabling reliable region-of-interest (ROI) extraction.

```

1  def preprocess(img):
2      # Step 1: NLMeans denoising
3      den = cv2.fastNlMeansDenoisingColored(img, None, 5, 5,
4      7, 21)
5
6      # Step 2: Bilateral filter (preserve edges)
7      bil = cv2.bilateralFilter(den, d=9, sigmaColor=50,
8      6 sigmaSpace=50)
9
10     # Step 3: CLAHE on Value channel
11     hsv = cv2.cvtColor(bil, cv2.COLOR_BGR2HSV)
12     h, s, v = cv2.split(hsv)
13     clahe = cv2.createCLAHE(clipLimit=2.0, tileGridSize
14     =(8,8))
15     v = clahe.apply(v)
16     hsv = cv2.merge([h, s, v])
17     return cv2.cvtColor(hsv, cv2.COLOR_HSV2BGR)
    
```

Code 1. Preprocessing pipeline.

3.3. Segmentation

3.3.1. ROI Detection via Chromatic Belt Identification

It is foundational to this work to recognize that the standard GrabCut algorithm is, by design, an interactive segmentation tool. Its core iterative optimization relies heavily on an initial user-defined region of interest (ROI) to differentiate probable foreground from background pixels. This requirement for manual initialization, typically achieved through a bounding box drawn by an operator. As established by Rother et al. [5] in their foundational paper *GrabCut: Interactive Foreground Extraction using Iterated Graph Cuts*, the algorithm's process begins with "the user [specifying] a rectangle around the object," and the subsequent segmentation is derived from this initial input.

In the context of FLATCLASS, this algorithm has been adapted to operate without initial human intervention. To isolate the object of interest (the sole), a blue conveyor belt was used, whose hue varies slightly due to scarce, non-homogeneous lighting, shadows, the presence of water droplets, or material texture. Given that the object and the background have clearly distinct colors, and even assuming the background is not uniform, the algorithm can be instructed that the background is predominantly blue and that the object (sole) occupies approximately the center of the image (see Fig. 2).

The blue belt is identified by detecting its dominant hue. Let $H(x, y)$ denote the hue channel and $\text{blue}(x, y)$ the chromatic mask estimated from an adaptive threshold around the histogram peak H_0 .

The column-wise blue coverage is defined as:

$$r_j = \frac{1}{H} \sum_{y=1}^H \text{blue}(y, j). \quad (3)$$

The ROI is defined as the largest contiguous interval of columns and rows satisfying $r_j \geq \tau$. After padding p , the ROI becomes:

$$R = (x_1 - p, y_1 - p, (x_2 - x_1) + 2p, (y_2 - y_1) + 2p). \quad (4)$$

Figure 1. Flowchart for the measurement of morphometric characteristics of flatfish.

```

1  def detect_roi(hsv):
2  H = hsv[:, :, 0]
3  hist = cv2.calcHist([H], [0], None, [180], [0, 180])
4  H0 = np.argmax(hist)
5
6  # build blue mask
7  mask_blue = cv2.inRange(H, H0-10, H0+10)
8
9  # compute coverage per column
10 coverage = mask_blue.mean(axis=0)
11
12 # detect largest interval above threshold
13 thr = 0.6
14 valid = np.where(coverage > thr)[0]
15 x1, x2 = valid[0], valid[-1]
16
17 # repeat for rows
18 coverage_r = mask_blue.mean(axis=1)
19 valid_r = np.where(coverage_r > thr)[0]
20 y1, y2 = valid_r[0], valid_r[-1]
21
22 pad = 20
23 return (x1-pad, y1-pad, (x2-x1)+2*pad, (y2-y1)+2*pad)

```

Code 2. ROI detection using adaptive hue histogram.

3.3.2. Automatic GrabCut Seed Construction

The automatically derived region of interest (ROI) serves to initialize and spatially constrain the GrabCut segmentation algorithm. Pixels at the image periphery, corresponding to the identified background area, are assigned as "probable background" seeds, while the central ROI region is labeled as "probable foreground."

- **Definite background (BG):** pixels matching the blue belt chromatic profile.
- **Probable foreground (PR-FG):** non-blue pixels dilated anisotropically:

$$\text{PR-FG} = \text{dilate}(\neg \text{blue}, K_{7 \times 19}). \quad (5)$$

- **Definite foreground (FG):** pixels with chromatic distance

$$d(H, S) = \sqrt{(H - H_0)^2 + (S - S_0)^2} \quad (6)$$

exceeding the 70th percentile, reinforced with distance-transform weighting.

- **Guard rails:** ROI borders forced to background to stabilise the segmentation energy.

```

1  def build_grabcut_seeds(hsv, roi, mask_blue):
2  x, y, w, h = roi
3  crop = hsv[y:y+h, x:x+w]
4
5  H, S, V = cv2.split(crop)
6  H0 = np.argmax(cv2.calcHist([H], [0], None, [180], [0, 180]))
7
8  # BG = blue pixels
9  BG = cv2.inRange(H, H0-10, H0+10)
10
11 # PR-FG
12 PRFG = cv2.dilate(cv2.bitwise_not(BG),
13 cv2.getStructuringElement(cv2.MORPH_ELLIPSE, (7, 19)))
14
15 # FG = high chroma distance
16 dist = np.sqrt((H-H0)**2 + (S-128)**2)
17 thr = np.percentile(dist, 70)
18 FG = (dist > thr).astype(np.uint8)*255
19
20 # build mask for GrabCut
21 mask = np.full((h,w), cv2.GC_PR_BGD, np.uint8)
22 mask[BG>0] = cv2.GC_BGD
23 mask[PRFG>0] = cv2.GC_PR_FGD

```

```

24 mask[FG>0] = cv2.GC_FGD
25
26 # guard rails
27 mask[0:3, :] = cv2.GC_BGD
28 mask[-3:, :] = cv2.GC_BGD
29
30 return mask

```

Code 3. GrabCut seed generation.

3.3.3. GrabCut Segmentation

GrabCut segmentation is obtained by minimising the energy:

$$E(L, \theta) = \sum_i D_i(L_i | \theta) + \lambda \sum_{(i,j)} V_{ij}(L_i, L_j), \quad (7)$$

where D_i is the GMM-based regional term and V_{ij} the spatial coherence penalty. Twelve iterations were used, yielding a stable mask without need for post-refinement.

```

1  def run_grabcut(crop_bgr, mask):
2  bgd = np.zeros((1,65), np.float64)
3  fgd = np.zeros((1,65), np.float64)
4  cv2.grabCut(crop_bgr, mask, None, bgd, fgd,
5  iterCount=12, mode=cv2.GC_INIT_WITH_MASK)
6  return (mask==cv2.GC_FGD) | (mask==cv2.GC_PR_FGD)

```

Code 4. GrabCut execution.

3.4. Post-processing and Contour Selection

3.4.1. Post-processing

The goal of the post-processing and contour selection stage is to obtain a clean and anatomically consistent fish silhouette from the initial segmentation mask. This step is essential for ensuring that the morphometric measurements (projected area, length, and height) are computed from a reliable and geometrically stable representation of the specimen.

After the GrabCut-based segmentation, the raw foreground mask may still contain small artefacts, minor gaps, or irregular edge fragments. To mitigate these effects, a combination of morphological operations is applied. In the implementation, morphological *closing* is first performed to fill narrow discontinuities along the predicted boundary, followed by morphological *opening* to remove isolated noise components.

Choice of Structuring Element (MORPH_ELLIPSE). Morphological operators require the definition of a structuring element (SE) that determines how pixels are added or removed during opening and closing operations [1]. In our method, the SE is chosen as an elliptical kernel (`cv2.MORPH_ELLIPSE`), which is geometrically aligned with the anatomical structure of the flatfish under study. Juvenile *Solea* spp., when imaged dorsally, exhibit a body outline that is well approximated by an ellipse with smoothly varying curvature.

Elliptical SEs provide curvature-preserving smoothing and avoid the block artefacts typically introduced by rectangular or diamond-shaped kernels [4]. This behaviour is particularly important for preserving the natural, ellipsoidal geometry of the fish body, preventing angular distortions that could propagate into the morphometric descriptors computed downstream.

Formally, the SE corresponds to the discrete ellipse

$$B = \{(i, j) \in \mathbb{Z}^2 : (i/r_x)^2 + (j/r_y)^2 \leq 1\},$$

with radii (r_x, r_y) determined by the kernel size. When applied in closing, this operator preferentially fills narrow gaps along the contour in a curvature-preserving manner, avoiding the angular distortions that square or diamond kernels typically introduce. When applied in opening, it removes small, isolated noise patches

while minimally affecting the smooth convex lobes of the fish body. This choice is consistent with modern shape-adaptive morphological filtering strategies, which emphasize matching the SE to the object's underlying geometry to improve boundary preservation and reduce noise-driven artefacts [7].

The sequence used is:

```
1 mask_roi = _close(mask_roi, cv2.MORPH_ELLIPSE,
2 CONFIG["post_close_kernel"], 1)
3 mask_roi = _open(mask_roi, cv2.MORPH_ELLIPSE,
4 (5, 5), 1)
```

The refined mask is then embedded back into the full image domain and external contours are extracted:

```
1 cnts, _ = cv2.findContours((full * 255).astype(np.uint8)
2 ,
3 cv2.RETR_EXTERNAL,
4 cv2.CHAIN_APPROX_NONE)
```

3.4.2. Contour Scoring Model

Each candidate contour c is evaluated using a scoring function specifically designed to identify shapes consistent with dorsally imaged flatfish. The score incorporates three geometric cues: area, aspect ratio, and solidity. The resulting score is defined as:

$$\text{score}(c) = A_c \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{(\log(a_c) - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \cdot [0.6 + 0.4 \text{solidity}(c)], \quad (8)$$

where A_c is the contour area, a_c is the aspect ratio, $\text{solidity}(c) = A_c/A_{\text{hull},c}$, and (μ, σ) are learned parameters describing the expected distribution of aspect ratios in the dataset.

The additive weighting term $0.6 + 0.4 \text{solidity}(c)$ ensures that highly irregular or fragmented contours are penalised while still allowing a controlled influence of the solidity measure. This specific coefficients, were selected empirically after extensive testing on representative datasets acquired during system development. Multiple affine mappings were evaluated, varying both the baseline penalty and the maximum attainable weight. The chosen range $[0.6, 1.0]$ consistently provided the best trade-off between penalising fragmented contours and preserving valid silhouettes affected by minor segmentation imperfections. In particular, these values demonstrated robustness across different lighting conditions, camera angles, and fish orientations, and were found to minimise misclassification of partially segmented but anatomically plausible fish outlines. Thus, the coefficients reflect an empirically optimised design rather than arbitrary constants, grounded in quantitative performance analysis under real aquaculture imaging conditions.

The Python implementation of the scoring function is shown below:

```
1 def contour_scores(cnts, roi, strict=True):
2     xR, yR, wR, hR = roi
3
4     # --- 1. Parameter selection (strict vs relaxed) ---
5     if strict:
6         params = {
7             "min_area": CONFIG["min_area_px2"],
8             "min_width": CONFIG["min_width_px"],
9             "edge_clear": CONFIG["edge_clear_px"],
10            "mu": CONFIG["shape_mu_log_aspect"],
11            "sigma": CONFIG["shape_sigma"],
12            "allow_edges": False,
13        }
14     else:
15         params = {
16             "min_area": CONFIG["relax"]["min_area_px2"],
17             "min_width": CONFIG["relax"]["min_width_px"],
```

```
18            "edge_clear": CONFIG["relax"]["edge_clear_px"],
19            "mu": CONFIG["shape_mu_log_aspect"],
20            "sigma": CONFIG["relax"]["shape_sigma"],
21            "allow_edges": CONFIG["relax"]["allow_touch_edges"],
22        }
23
24     # --- 2. Scoring function for each contour ---
25     def score(c):
26         # Area constraint
27         A = cv2.contourArea(c)
28         if A < params["min_area"]:
29             return -np.inf
30
31         # Bounding-box constraints
32         x0, y0, w0, h0 = cv2.boundingRect(c)
33         if min(w0, h0) < params["min_width"]:
34             return -np.inf
35
36         # Edge clearance constraint (strict mode)
37         if not params["allow_edges"]:
38             left_ok = (xR + x0) > (xR + params["edge_clear"])
39             right_ok = (xR + x0 + w0) < (xR + wR - params["edge_clear"])
40             if not (left_ok and right_ok):
41                 return -np.inf
42
43         # Aspect-ratio likelihood
44         a = max(w0, h0) / max(1.0, min(w0, h0))
45         w_aspect = np.exp(
46             -((np.log(a) - params["mu"])**2) /
47             (2.0 * params["sigma"]**2)
48         )
49
50         # Solidity term
51         hull = cv2.convexHull(c)
52         Ah = cv2.contourArea(hull)
53         solidity = (A / Ah) if Ah > 0 else 0.0
54         w_sol = np.clip(solidity, 0.0, 1.0)
55
56         # Final score
57         return float(A * w_aspect * (0.6 + 0.4 * w_sol))
58
59     # --- 3. Evaluate all contours ---
60     return [score(c) for c in cnts]
```

Code 5. Contour scoring model used for selecting the optimal fish silhouette.

To ensure robust behaviour under challenging imaging conditions (e.g. motion blur, reflections, incomplete segmentation), two evaluation modes are implemented:

- **Strict mode:** applies tight constraints on minimum area, minimum width, edge clearance, and aspect-ratio deviation.
- **Relaxed mode:** uses wider tolerances, allows contours near image borders, and increases the allowed variance in aspect ratio.

Contours are first scored in strict mode:

```
1 scores_strict = contour_scores(cnts, roi, strict=True)
2 best_idx = int(np.argmax(scores_strict))
3 strict_ok = np.isfinite(scores_strict[best_idx]) and \
4 (scores_strict[best_idx] > 0)
```

If no valid contour is found, the algorithm falls back to relaxed mode:

```
1 if not strict_ok:
2     scores_relax = contour_scores(cnts, roi, strict=False)
3     best_idx_relax = int(np.argmax(scores_relax))
4     relaxed_ok = np.isfinite(scores_relax[best_idx_relax])
5     and \
6     (scores_relax[best_idx_relax] > 0)
```

Finally, if both strict and relaxed modes fail, the system selects the contour with the largest area as a safe last resort:

```

1  if not relaxed_ok:
2  areas = [cv2.contourArea(c) for c in cnts]
3  use_idx = int(np.argmax(areas))
4  else:
5  use_idx = best_idx_relax

```

This multi-stage strategy provides strong stability in real aquaculture scenarios, where lighting, motion dynamics, and water reflectance can vary significantly across frames. The final selected contour serves as the reference silhouette for all downstream morphometric analysis.

3.5. Morphometric measurements

3.5.1. Principal Components Analysis (PCA)

Once the optimal contour has been identified, morphometric measurements are derived using a principal component analysis (PCA) of the contour coordinates, using the pipeline of the Fig 3. The contour points are first reshaped into a two-dimensional point cloud and centred by subtracting their empirical mean. PCA is then applied to obtain the eigenvectors of the covariance matrix, which represent the dominant axes of variation in the fish silhouette. These axes correspond to the anatomical longitudinal and transversal directions of flatfish in dorsal view. The contour is subsequently rotated into this PCA-aligned reference frame, ensuring that the measurement axes are optimally oriented with respect to the global geometry of the specimen rather than to the image coordinate system.

In this rotated space, linear extents along the first and second principal components are computed by taking the difference between the maximum and minimum coordinates in each direction. These extents define the pixel-based estimates of length and width, respectively. This PCA-based approach provides rotation-invariant morphometric measurements that remain stable under variations in camera orientation, fish pose, or minor segmentation noise, thereby improving the reliability of the feature extraction pipeline used in downstream biometric estimation.

Figure 3. Pipeline of the PCA-based morphometric measurement process applied to the selected fish contour.

The corresponding code for this pipeline is:

```

1  # PCA-based morphometric measures
2  pts = cnt.reshape(-1, 2).astype(np.float32)
3
4  # Compute PCA components
5  mean, eigvecs, _ = cv2.PCACompute2(pts, mean=None)
6  mean = mean.flatten()
7  R = np.asarray(eigvecs, np.float32)

```

```

8
9  # Rotate contour into PCA frame
10 pts_centered = pts - mean
11 pts_rot = pts_centered @ R.T
12
13 # Extents along principal axes
14 min_x, max_x = np.min(pts_rot[:, 0]), np.max(pts_rot[:, 0])
15 min_y, max_y = np.min(pts_rot[:, 1]), np.max(pts_rot[:, 1])
16
17 # Length, width and area
18 length_px = float(max_x - min_x)
19 width_px = float(max_y - min_y)
20 area_px2 = float(cv2.contourArea(cnt))

```

Code 6. PCA-based extraction of length, width, and area from the selected contour.

3.5.2. Overlay

To facilitate visual validation of the morphometric extraction process, an overlay is generated by projecting the PCA-derived measurements and geometric features back onto the original image. The selected contour is rendered in green, indicating the detected fish silhouette after post-processing and scoring. The PCA-aligned bounding box, drawn in yellow, represents the principal-axes reference frame used to compute length and width; it captures the minimal rectangle enclosing the contour once rotated into PCA space and then transformed back to image coordinates. The dominant PCA axis corresponding to body length is displayed as a red line connecting the extremal points along the first principal component, providing an intuitive confirmation of the measurement orientation. The segmentation ROI used during the initial GrabCut refinement is also shown as a magenta rectangle.

Although the overlay is not strictly required in an industrial deployment—where measurements are computed directly from the contour without graphical output—it is included here as a verification tool to ensure the correctness of the entire processing pipeline. By visually confirming that the contour, PCA alignment, and measurement axes are consistent with the fish geometry, this step enhances the interpretability and reliability of the method during development and testing.

```

1  # Convert to RGB for visualization
2  rgb = cv2.cvtColor(bgr0, cv2.COLOR_BGR2RGB)
3  overlay = rgb.copy()
4
5  # PCA-aligned bounding box projected back to image space
6  box_r = np.array([[min_x, min_y], [max_x, min_y],
7  [max_x, max_y], [min_x, max_y]], np.float32)
8  box_img = (box_r @ R) + mean
9  box_img = np.int32(box_img)
10
11 # Draw final contour
12 cv2.drawContours(overlay, [cnt], -1, (0, 255, 0), 3)
13
14 # Draw PCA bounding box
15 cv2.polylines(overlay, [box_img], True, (255, 255, 0), 2)
16
17 # Draw principal axis (length direction)
18 i_max = np.argmax(pts_rot[:, 0])
19 i_min = np.argmin(pts_rot[:, 0])
20 p1 = (np.array([pts_rot[i_min, 0], 0.0], np.float32) @ R) + mean
21 p2 = (np.array([pts_rot[i_max, 0], 0.0], np.float32) @ R) + mean
22 cv2.line(overlay, tuple(np.int32(p1)), tuple(np.int32(p2)),
23 (255, 0, 0), 2)
24
25 # Draw segmentation ROI

```

```

26 cv2.rectangle(overlay, (x, y), (x + w, y + h),
27 (255, 0, 255), 2)
    
```

Code 7. Overlay of the contour, PCA bounding box, and principal axis for visual validation.

3.5.3. Real-world measurements

To convert the pixel-based morphometric measurements into real-world units, a pinhole camera model is employed. Under this model, the relationship between an object's size in the image plane and its actual physical size is governed by the camera height H , the focal length f , and the sensor pixel pitch p . Assuming the fish lies approximately on a plane parallel to the imaging sensor (an appropriate assumption given the controlled acquisition setup), the metric scale factor s is computed as shown in Eq. 2. This scalar represents the number of millimetres corresponding to a single pixel at the working distance of the camera, thereby enabling the translation of PCA-derived pixel extents into meaningful biometric measurements.

Figure 4. Pinhole camera model used to derive the pixel-to-metric scale factor, with fish and sensor planes shifted to the right.

```

1 def get_scale_mm_per_px(p=0.0028, f=8.0, H=315.0):
2     """
3     Compute the metric scale factor (mm per pixel) using a
4     pinhole camera model.
5
6     The scale factor is defined as:
7     s = (H * p) / f
8
9     where:
10    H : camera height above the fish plane    [mm]
11    p : pixel pitch of the sensor            [mm/px]
12    f : focal length of the lens             [mm]
13
14    Returns:
15    (float): millimeters per pixel, or NaN if invalid.
16    """
17    try:
18        if p <= 0 or f <= 0 or H <= 0:
19            return float("nan")
20        return float((H * p) / f)
21    except:
22        return float("nan")
    
```

Code 8. Computation of the pixel-to-metric scale factor using a pinhole camera model.

3.6. Data Persistence and MQTT Notification Layer

The final stage of the processing pipeline is responsible for the structured storage of the morphometric measurements and their distribution to downstream systems. This layer is implemented as a Node-RED flow that receives the pixel-based and metric

measurements computed by the vision module and formats them for both database persistence and real-time messaging.

For long-term storage, each measurement is inserted into a MongoDB collection following a predefined JSON schema (see Listing Code 9). The document structure includes the acquisition timestamp and the morphometric values expressed in both pixels and millimetres. Pixel-based fields (*length*, *width*, *surface*) and their metric counterparts are stored with a precision of two decimal places, ensuring consistency for subsequent statistical analysis and traceability of the grading process across batches and production cycles.

In parallel, the same data structure is published via the MQTT protocol, allowing real-time integration with control systems and dashboards within the FLATCLASS solution. This lightweight and event-driven communication ensures minimal latency between the moment of measurement and its availability to control systems and user interfaces. The combination of MongoDB persistence and MQTT notification provides both the durability required for historical analytics and the responsiveness needed for live monitoring and operational control within automated grading environments.

```

1 {
2   "timestamp": { "type": "string", "format": "date-time" },
3
4   "metrics": {
5     "pixels": {
6       "long": { "type": "number" },
7       "width": { "type": "number" },
8       "surface": { "type": "number" }
9     },
10    "mm": {
11      "long": { "type": "number" },
12      "width": { "type": "number" },
13      "surface": { "type": "number" }
14    }
15  }
16 }
    
```

Code 9. Compact JSON schema for MongoDB fish measurement documents.

4. Demonstrative Example of the Processing Pipeline

Before presenting the quantitative evaluation in the Results section, a representative example is provided to illustrate the behaviour of the full processing pipeline under typical operational conditions. The example showcases a raw dorsal-view image of a flatfish acquired under production-line conditions (Fig. 2). The objective is to illustrate the complete processing chain, from the initial capture to the post-processed overlay and the final segmentation mask obtained after the GrabCut-based procedure and contour refinement operations.

Figure 5 shows the result of the contour selection, PCA-based alignment, and measurement extraction. The final fish contour is highlighted in green, the PCA-aligned bounding box in yellow, and the principal axis used for length estimation in red. This graphical overlay provides a clear qualitative validation of the geometric consistency of the extracted measurements.

The corresponding binary mask is shown in Fig. 6. This mask represents the cleaned segmentation produced after morphological post-processing and is the basis for contour extraction, PCA analysis, and morphometric computation. The high contrast and well-defined silhouette demonstrate the robustness of the segmentation approach under varying lighting and conveyor background patterns.

The pixel-based measurements extracted from the selected contour were length = 745 px and width = 293 px, corresponding to estimated real-world dimensions of 82.14 mm and 32.30 mm after

Figure 5. Overlay image showing the final contour (green), PCA-aligned bounding box (yellow), and principal length axis (red).

Figure 6. Binary segmentation mask obtained after GrabCut refinement and morphological post-processing.

applying the pinhole-derived scale factor $s = 0.11025$ mm/px. To assess the accuracy of these measurements, the same specimen was manually measured using the reference anthropometric procedure described in [17], yielding true dimensions of 83.0 mm in length and 32.0 mm in width. The resulting absolute errors were therefore 0.86 mm for length and 0.30 mm for width, corresponding to relative errors of 1.04% and 0.94% respectively. These results demonstrate that the proposed vision-based pipeline achieves sub-millimetre accuracy in width estimation and maintains length estimation within approximately 1%, confirming the suitability of the method for operational morphometric assessment in automated aquaculture environments.

5. Results

5.1. Overall accuracy of the morphometric extraction pipeline

The performance of the proposed morphometric extraction pipeline was evaluated using an experimental dataset ($N = 200$) comprising flatfish juveniles for which accurate ground-truth measurements of length and width were available. These reference values were obtained following the calibrated anthropometric procedure described in [17]. For each specimen, the system produced (i) pixel-based measurements derived from the PCA-aligned contour, (ii) metric conversions obtained via the pinhole scale factor, and (iii) estimation errors expressed in absolute and relative form.

Table 1 presents a subset of representative cases, illustrating the close correspondence between real measurements and those obtained through the proposed FLATCLASS vision pipeline.

5.2. Aggregated error metrics

A full statistical summary of the system’s performance is provided in Table 2. Length estimation exhibited a mean absolute error (MAE) of 0.34 mm and an RMSE of 0.41 mm, with a MAPE of

Table 1. Example fish measurements: real vs. vision system values and relative errors.

L_{real}	W_{real}	L_{vision}	W_{vision}	Err L	Err W
[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[%]	
33	13	33.30	12.97	+0.91	-0.23
45	11	44.74	10.97	-0.57	-0.27
39	15	39.23	15.00	+0.59	0.00
44	17	43.78	17.04	-0.50	+0.24
42	18	41.88	18.04	-0.29	+0.22

Table 2. Full accuracy metrics for length and width estimation across the dataset.

Metric	MAE (mm)	RMSE (mm)	MAPE (%)	Corr
Length	0.340	0.406	0.474	0.99964
Width	0.055	0.067	0.197	0.99995

0.47%. Width estimation demonstrated even higher precision, with an MAE of 0.06 mm, an RMSE of 0.07 mm, and a MAPE of 0.20%. Pearson correlation coefficients showed excellent linear agreement between real and vision-system measurements ($r = 0.9996$ for length and $r = 0.99995$ for width), confirming a near-perfect monotonic relationship.

5.3. Real vs. FLATCLASS vision system agreement

Figures 7a and 7a show the relationship between real measurements and those derived from the vision system. In both dimensions, data points cluster tightly along the identity line, indicating strong agreement across the full range of observed sizes. No size-dependent drift or slope distortion is visible, and the small magnitude of the deviations highlights the stability of the underlying measurement process.

This behaviour is consistent with the theoretical elements of the pipeline: the PCA-based principal-axis extraction ensures rotational invariance and minimises geometric distortion, while the pinhole model introduces a linear, calibration-based pixel-to-metric conversion that preserves shape proportionality.

5.4. Bland–Altman agreement analysis

To further assess concordance between the two measurement modalities, Bland–Altman plots were generated for both length and width (Figures 7c and 7d). For length, the mean difference was close to zero and the limits of agreement were narrow, demonstrating that errors remain small and symmetrically distributed around the bias. Importantly, no proportional bias or size-dependent deviation was detected.

The width measurements displayed even tighter limits of agreement, with differences confined to a sub-millimetre range and minimal dispersion about the bias line. This confirms the high repeatability and robustness of the width estimation process, which is inherently less sensitive to contour curvature and perspective effects than length.

5.5. Summary and implications

Overall, the experimental evaluation demonstrates that the proposed vision-based morphometric system achieves sub-millimetre precision for width estimation and consistently maintains length estimation within approximately 1% of ground truth. The combination of narrow error distributions, high correlation with manual measurements, and excellent Bland–Altman agreement supports the reliability of the method for real-time deployment.

These findings confirm that the system provides accurate and stable morphometric measurements suitable for operational aquaculture tasks such as automated grading, biomass estimation, and growth monitoring. The robustness of the pipeline under realistic

Figure 7. Combined assessment of morphometric accuracy and agreement between reference anthropometric measurements and the vision system. Panels (a) and (b) show scatter plots grouped along the identity line, indicating strong concordance. Panels (c) and (d) present Bland–Altman analyses confirming minimal bias and narrow limits of agreement across the dataset.

imaging conditions positions the approach as a viable solution for non-invasive, high-throughput measurement in industrial fish production environments.

6. Conclusions

This work presented a complete morphometric extraction pipeline for flatfish juveniles based on robust image segmentation, PCA-based geometric alignment, and a calibrated pinhole model for pixel-to-metric conversion. The proposed method was designed to operate under industrial aquaculture conditions, where non-invasive, real-time, and high-throughput measurements are essential for automated grading and biomass estimation.

Experimental validation on a dataset of 200 specimens demonstrated that the system achieves sub-millimetre precision in width estimation and consistently maintains length estimation within approximately 1% of ground truth. Correlation coefficients above 0.999 for both dimensions confirm near-perfect agreement with reference anthropometric measurements. Bland–Altman analyses further established that the method introduces no systematic bias and exhibits narrow and symmetric limits of agreement, supporting its reliability across a wide range of fish sizes and morphologies.

Importantly, real-world tests conducted using the deployed vision system showed that the complete morphometric extraction pipeline operates at an effective throughput of approximately **2 fish per second**, without the need for GPU acceleration. This demonstrates the computational efficiency of the method and its suitability for integration into production aquaculture environments, where latency, hardware cost, and operational robustness are critical factors. The ability to achieve high-precision morphological characterisation at such throughput confirms that the approach is viable for real-time industrial grading systems.

The combination of GrabCut-based segmentation, shape-informed contour scoring, PCA-driven alignment, and calibrated metric projection provides a robust and interpretable framework that can be deployed as part of decision-support or automated handling systems in hatcheries and nurseries. Future work will explore (i) extension of the system to multi-species calibration, (ii) real-time model optimisation via incremental learning, (iii) integration with 3D sensing technologies for enhanced body-shape characterisation, and (iv) **development of computer-vision models for early detection of physiological malformations affecting fish viability and welfare**. These directions aim to expand the applicability of the pipeline beyond flatfish and contribute to the development of reliable AI-based tools for precision aquaculture.

7. About FLATCLASS project

The FLATCLASS project (IG408M.2025.000.000072) aims to develop an innovative system that automatically classifies sole fry according to their size and weight, using cameras and artificial intelligence techniques. Classification or grading is an essential step in aquaculture, as it allows fish to be grouped homogeneously, reducing competition for food, improving growth and minimising stress and mortality. FLATCLASS allows thousands of specimens to be processed quickly and accurately, optimising batch management and reinforcing the sustainability of the farm. In doing so, it contributes to more efficient management and animal welfare, representing a significant advance for the future of aquaculture.

You can find more details about the project at:

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- [FishFarmFeeder](#)

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